

Novel graphical method for the simultaneous determination of stability constant and molar absorptivity of some metal – Chrome Azurol S complexes

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Abstract : Stability constants and molar absorptivities of complexes formed by Chrome Azurol S (tri sodium salt of 3''-sulpho-2''-6''-dichloro-3:3'-dimethyl-4-hydroxy-fuschsone-5:5-dicarboxy acid) with metal ions like Al^{III}, Sc^{II}, Cu^{II}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI} ions have been determined by a novel graphical method in which neither the concentration of ligand has to be kept high in comparison to the concentration of metal ion nor any term has to be omitted to get the linear equation.

Keywords : Metal complexes, CAS, stability constant, molar absorptivity.

Introduction

The dyes of hydroxy triphenyl methane group have a tendency to form coloured chelates with metal ions in solution. The pronounced chelating properties of these dyes are due to the presence of donar groups like -COOH, -OH and -O. Chelates involving several metal ions have been reported¹. The spectrophotometric investigation of Fe^{III}-Chrome Azurol S (CAS) was carried out by Langmyhr and Klausen². Because of characteristic colour formation with metal ion CAS is used as spot reagent, as metallochromic indicator in complexometric titration³ and spectrophotometric reagents for the determination and extraction of micro amounts of heavy metals in environmental samples⁴⁻⁷. Ravison and Harley described spectrophotometric determination of fluoride ion, which prevents the full colour development of the thorium-CAS lake⁸.

Chrome Azurol S (CAS), tri sodium salt of 3''-sulpho-2''-6''-dichloro-3:3'-dimethyl-4-hydroxy-fuschsone-5:5-dicarboxy acid (colour mordant blue – 29, C.I. 43835) is an important member of this family (Scheme 1).

In the case of CAS chelate, there are two alternative positions of the chelate ring. The metal ion may be coordinated either between (i) the quinoid oxygen and the

Scheme 1

adjacent oxygen of the carboxylic group or (ii) the phenolic oxygen and the adjacent carboxylic oxygen. On the basis of the decrease in the pH when hydrogen ions are liberated as a result of the chelation, as in the case of normal group elements, the hydroxyl oxygen participates in the chelation. On the other hand, no change in pH occurs in the reaction with the transition and rare earth elements. In such cases chelation appears to occur between the quinoid oxygen and the adjacent carboxylic oxygen.

In this paper the stability constant and molar absorptivities of 1 : 1 complexes formed by CAS with Al^{III}, Sc^{III}, Cu^{II}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI} ions were determined by novel graphical method. The value of molar absorptivity reflects the sensitivity of the method.

Results and discussion

A series of solutions were prepared by mixing said metal ions and CAS solutions in 1 : 1 ratio. The absorbance of each solution was recorded for the corresponding λ_{\max} .

For the formation of 1 : 1 complex species according to the eq. (1),

the stability constant (K) can be expressed as eq. (2),

$$K = \frac{[ML]}{\{[M^0] - [ML]\}\{[L^0] - [ML]\}} \quad (2)$$

where, M^0 and L^0 are the analytical concentration of metal ion and ligand respectively and $[ML]$ is the equilibrium concentration of the complex, ML . If metal ion, ligand and complex absorb light in the region of study, the absorbance (A) for unit path length can be expressed as eq. (3),

$$A = \{[M^0] - [ML]\}\epsilon_M + \{[L^0] - [ML]\}\epsilon_L + [ML]\epsilon_C \quad (3)$$

where, ϵ_M , ϵ_L and ϵ_C are the molar extinction coefficient of the species M , L and ML respectively.

Combining eqs. (2) and (3) and rearranging we get eq. (4),

$$\frac{M^0L^0}{A - \epsilon} + \frac{A - \epsilon}{\epsilon_0^2} = \frac{M^0 + L^0}{\epsilon_0} + \frac{1}{K\epsilon_0} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where, } \epsilon = M^0\epsilon_M + L^0\epsilon_L \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and } \epsilon_0 = \epsilon_C - \epsilon_M - \epsilon_L \quad (6)$$

If the left hand side of eq. (4) is plotted against $M^0 + L^0$ (Fig. 1), one will get a slope as $1/\epsilon_0$ and intercept as

Fig. 1

$1/K\epsilon_0$. From these one can calculate K . Usually the value of ϵ_C is not known initially, nor the value of ϵ_0 . In such case, a trial value of ϵ_0 can be taken and approximate values of ϵ_0 and K are calculated. The approximate value of ϵ_0 can be refined by successive approximations using method of least squares.

It was observed that in second and subsequent iterations the value of ϵ_0 decreases and K increases. The process was continued till two successive values were the same. The results are summarised in Table 1.

This novel graphical method has three clear cut benefits, firstly, no term is omitted, secondly, only 1 : 1 complex is formed since equimolar amounts of metal and ligand is taken, hence there is no possibility of the formation of 1 : 2 complex and lastly the most important advantage of this method is that stability constant and molar absorptivity can be determined simultaneously.

Table 1. Experimental data and results; temperature : Al^{III} -, Cu^{II} -, Th^{IV} - and UO_2^{II} -CAS : (30 °C), Sc^{III} -CAS : (25 °C)

System	Concentration range $\times 10^5$ (M)	pH ± 0.2	Ionic strength (M)	λ_{\max} (nm)	$\epsilon_0 \times 10^{-3}$ (L.M. ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	log K_1
Al^{III} -CAS	1.33-3.32	5.0	0.2	545	44.41	4.35
Sc^{III} -CAS	1.00-2.50	5.0	0.2	560	65.62	5.18
Cu^{II} -CAS	2.50-6.25	6.5	0.1	560	26.04	4.50
Th^{IV} -CAS	2.50-5.00	4.5	0.15	550	53.24	4.21
UO_2^{II} -CAS	1.00-2.50	5.0	0.15	570	5.95	4.22

Experimental

Solutions were prepared in 1 : 1 ratio by mixing known amount of $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, ScCl_3 , CuSO_4 , ThCl_4 , UO_2SO_4 (B.D.H.) and CAS (E. Merck). The pH was adjusted between 4 to 6.5 ± 0.05 as per the system by adding dilute perchloric acid or dilute solution of sodium hydroxide and the ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 M for Al-CAS system, 0.15 M for Th-CAS system and 0.1 M for Cu-CAS system using sodium perchlorate (B D.H) solution. The composition of complexes formed at pH 4 to 6.5 ± 0.05 is 1 : 1 as obtained by the method of continuous variations⁹.

A set of nine solutions of 1 : 1 molar ratio for each system were prepared and the absorbance values were recorded at the corresponding λ_{max} values.

In case of Cu-CAS system both metal and ligand absorb light in the region of interest. So ϵ is evaluated as eq. (5).

In rest of the systems, only ligand absorbs light in the region of interest and hence

$$\epsilon_M = 0, \text{ therefore, } \epsilon = L^0 \epsilon_L$$

References

- 1 A K Dey, *Mikrochim Acta*, 1964, 2-4, 414
- 2 E J Langmyhr and K S Klausen, *Anal Chim Acta*, 1963, 29, 149
- 3 T Matsuo, *Japan Analyst*, 1958, 7, 149
- 4 M Shenker, Y Hadar and Y Chen, *J Soil Sci Soc Amer*, 1995, 59, 1612
- 5 D B do Nascimento and G Schwedt, *Mikrochim Acta*, 1997, 126, 159
- 6 L L Zhang, W Z Zheng, J W Lin and W Zeng, *Guang Pu Xue Yu Guang Pu Fen Xi*, 2006, 26, 529
- 7 M Behram, T Madrakian, E Bozorgzadeh and A Afkhami, *Talanta*, 2007, 72, 408
- 8 D Revison and J H Harley, *Anal Chem*, 1953, 25, 794
- 9 F J C Rossotti and H S Rossotti, "The Determination of Stability Constants", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1961